

Interim report semi-structured interviews

Deliverable D6.5

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D6.5 Interim report semi-structured interviews

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List of Abbreviations

CCS	Carbon capture and storage
CCU	Carbon capture and utilisation
CCUS	Carbon capture, utilisation and storage
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable (D6.5) report discusses the results obtained during individual interviews with carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS) stakeholders. The semi-structured interviews with CCUS stakeholders focused on collecting the participants' perspectives on what are the main enablers and barriers to CCUS implementation in Europe. The participants represented diverse CCUS stakeholder groups from the public, private, and civil society sectors. Further steps of the study will implement qualitative system dynamics modelling (Meadows, 2008b) and Group Model Building (Vennix, 1996) methods to analyse the causal relationships influencing CCUS implementation in Europe and to identify possible intervention points to alleviate barriers and strengthen enablers.

Understanding the perspectives of stakeholders on the challenges and opportunities for implementing CCUS is crucial for effectively reducing industrial carbon emissions. High-emitting industries play a crucial role in modern economies and decarbonisation, but at the same time account for approximately a quarter of energy-related emissions (IEA, 2023b, 2023c). CCUS technologies, which capture, store, or use CO₂ emissions, offer a promising solution for reducing the carbon emissions of these industries (IEA, 2021). However, the deployment of CCUS faces diverse economic, technical, social, governance and political challenges (Ashworth et al., 2010; Covarrubias et al., 2024; Määttä, Covarrubias, & Gooyert, 2024).

Insights from stakeholders play a crucial role in navigating these complexities and ensuring the effective integration of CCUS technologies with other decarbonisation strategies, such as renewable energy and hydrogen adoption (IEA, 2020; Määttä, Covarrubias, & Gooyert, 2024). The stakeholders interviewed for this study are key players in implementing CCUS projects across Europe and are actively involved in debates on CCUS policy. Engaging with these stakeholders provides valuable knowledge that can lead to more efficient, feasible, and socially responsible CCUS implementation (Kleanthis et al., 2022; Määttä, Fantini, et al., 2024).

Many CCUS implementation challenges are already well-known, such as the difficulties with the economic feasibility of projects (IEA, 2023a), the chicken-and-egg dilemma between capture, transport and storage projects (CCUS Forum, 2023b), and social acceptance of CCUS technologies (Terwel et al., 2012; van Egmond & Hekkert, 2015). The chicken-and-egg dilemma refers to the challenge of which should come first, capture projects or transport and storage projects. Many more challenges were identified based on the stakeholder interviews, and the participants also emphasised the complexity of the already well-known challenges. Additionally, the interview participants suggested enablers to support CCUS implementation.

The analysis conducted for this report is based on a preliminary analysis of the interviews and focused on reporting the key issues raised by the participants. The report does not discuss how the findings fit into the existing literature on CCUS or how the different enablers and barriers fit together. The more in-depth analysis will be undertaken in future outputs of Task 6.3 of the CaLby2030 project.

The next section will explain the methods, semi-structured expert interviews, data, and content analysis. Section Three will report the key barriers and enablers to CCUS implementation in Europe raised by the participants, and briefly reflect on the insights the interview provided on Calcium Looping carbon capture technology. Last, Section Four will discuss the findings and Section Five will conclude the report.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 What are semi-structured interviews

Qualitative methods aim at an in-depth understanding of phenomena. Qualitative interviews are the most common qualitative data collection method (Jamshed, 2014). The interviews in this study were semi-structured, meaning that the interviews were guided by general themes and topics that the interviewer aimed to cover (Jamshed, 2014), but the exact questions asked to each participant varied based on the expertise area of the participant and the discussion between the participant and the interviewer. All the questions with semi-structured interviews are open-ended. Interviews are a particularly useful method for gaining information on how people think and what they believe (Knott et al., 2022). The interviews were conducted online in Microsoft Teams, lasted between 30 and 75 minutes, and took place between November 2023 and June 2024. The interviews were recorded with participant consent.

2.2 Interview participant overview

The participants for the interviews were carefully selected using a variety of methods. The criteria for selection required them to be actively engaged in CCUS implementation or discussions within Europe, thus possessing expertise and experience in CCUS. As part of the preliminary study phase, the researchers examined the consultation process of the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy in Europe, a vital step in identifying key players involved in CCUS activities (Määttä, Covarrubias, & Gooyert, 2024). Furthermore, the researchers actively attended public events focused on CCUS and utilised personal networks to identify suitable interview participants. Invitations for the interviews were sent via email. Out of 59 invitations, 12 interviews were completed. Some participants also extended the invitations to other members within their organisations, increasing the number of people with whom the invitation was shared. The 12 interviews were considered adequate due to the data richness, the interviews serving as an initial data collection step, and the identification of numerous barriers and enablers (see e.g. Swennenhuis et al., 2024). The interviewed stakeholders represented diverse sectors, including private, public, and civil society actors, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Stakeholder categories

STAKEHOLDER CATEGORY	N
Company/business	4
Industry Association	1
Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO)	1
Academic/research organisation	2
Government/public sector	1
Environmental organisation	1
Consultant/advisory organisation	2
Total	12

The participants brought expertise in areas such as energy and climate policy, CCUS research, markets, and various industry sectors (see Table 2). While all participants were knowledgeable about CCUS broadly, they also contributed more specific insights within their areas of expertise. Notably, two participants were specialists in industrial decarbonisation across disciplines.

Table 2: Expertise areas of the stakeholders

EXPERTISE AREA (CAN BE MORE THAN ONE PER PARTICIPANT) ALL PARTICIPANTS ARE CCUS EXPERTS	N
Energy and climate policy	3
Academic/research	2
Iron and steel industry	3
Carbon capture and electricity markets	2
Cement industry	1
Industrial decarbonisation	2
Bioenergy/forestry	1

The participants were experts in carbon capture, utilisation, and storage in Europe and other parts of the world. The interview discussions mainly focused on Europe, with specific discussions about Denmark, Finland, Sweden, Germany, the Netherlands, Spain, Hungary, Norway, Romania, Belgium, France, the United Kingdom, and Poland. The interviews indicated that in Europe, CCUS is naturally a broader-level discussion due to recent EU-level developments, with limited developments at national levels.

2.3 Research ethics and data management

This study has received ethical approval from Radboud University Nijmegen School of Management. The interview participants were provided with information about the study and how the data would be processed, stored, and used, and filled out a consent form before the study (see Annex 2). The consent form included three different consents, and the participants could choose not to consent to all points. First, the participants could provide consent to participate in the study. Second, they could provide consent to the recording of the interview. The interview recordings were transcribed and pseudonymised. Last, they could provide consent to the sharing of the pseudonymised research transcripts for future studies. Ten of the participants consented to the sharing of the pseudonymised interview transcripts for future studies. In the cases when the participant provided written consent for it, the pseudonymised versions of the interviews will be published online in Zenodo, to follow open data principles.

2.4 Interview protocol

A generic version of the interview protocol can be found in Annex 1. This generic version was modified based on the specific expertise of each participant. The overarching research question was 'What are the main enablers and barriers to CCUS implementation in Europe?'. In many cases, the participant covered topics already in previous questions or may not have had expertise in the specific area.

2.5 Data analysis

The content analysis of the interviews focused on identifying the key problems and barriers to CCUS implementation in Europe, as well as the solutions (enablers) participants proposed. Section Three presents two tables that outline and describe these key barriers and enablers. Barriers refer to challenges or obstacles that hinder CCUS deployment, while enablers are solutions that could support its deployment or help overcome these barriers.

The qualitative content analysis began with a careful reading of the transcribed interviews, followed by coding the text to identify key barriers and enablers (Knott et al., 2022) with the help of Atlas.ti qualitative analysis software. The codes were then categorised. A total of 141 different codes were identified in the interviews, categorised into 9 barrier themes and 8 enabler themes.

This report is based on a preliminary analysis of the data. Further in-depth analysis will be conducted in future outputs of Task 6.3.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Key barriers to CCUS deployment in Europe

Table 3 describes all the key challenges raised by the interview participants. Section 3.2 identifies and describes the enablers connected to these challenges and Section Four discusses the challenges and enablers in more detail.

Table 3: Key barriers to CCUS implementation

KEY BARRIERS TO CCUS DEPLOYMENT		
BARRIER CATEGORY	How many of the interviews raised this as a key barrier?	DESCRIPTION
Acceptance	10	Public perceptions and social acceptance were raised as key challenges by the stakeholders, although two of the participants stated that the challenge is not as severe as is often portrayed. The acceptance barrier relates to public willingness to pay for more sustainable products, and project implementation, particularly the possibility of onshore storage across the EU.
CO ₂ transport and storage infrastructure	11	The development of CO ₂ storage infrastructure was one of the most commonly raised challenges by the participants. This challenge has many dimensions. Some of the participants discussed the chicken-and-egg dilemma, referring to how the investment decisions on capture, storage and transport projects relies on one another, resulting in a dilemma of which should go first. The infrastructure development is also a very collaborative challenge, hindered by challenges with cross-border transport arrangements, lack of coordination, and uncertainty around long-term storage liability. One of the participants also argued that taken into consideration the scope of the challenge, the current targets are not ambitious enough. Other participants raised the issue that currently as onshore CO ₂ storage is non-existent in Europe, and the storage development is concentrated in the North Sea, this risks leaving South and East Europe behind.

Collaboration	11	<p>The participants saw collaboration as an essential part of CCUS implementation in Europe, but that this is hindered by lack of shared CO₂ standards which hinders the sharing of CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure. Still, at the same time, introducing standards can also increase costs for capture projects, as they would need to make additional investments to meet the standards. Collaboration is also hindered by a lack of shared language between stakeholders, idealism, stakeholder fatigue, profit-seeking, and unwillingness to share sensitive company information.</p>
Holistic approach	11	<p>The participants problematised a lack of a holistic approach and the introduction of counterproductive measures. This holistic perspective included problematisation of the access to affordable clean energy to power CCUS processes, fragmented development of funding, coordination, and carbon accounting principles, and hype cycles. Three of the participants discussed how hype cycles can be a distraction or lead to a lack of holistic perspective. Four of the participants also discussed the broader global perspective and how the difference between European sustainability goals and global sustainability ambitions can negatively impact the competitiveness of European industries, which can result in carbon-emitting industries leakage.</p>
Economic	12	<p>The economic challenges raised by the participants were manifold and usually the economic challenges were seen as the most pressing challenges. The key elements of this challenge include the lack of a business case, lack of financial incentives, the cost and energy demand, cost and length of permitting processes, lack of action on demand side incentivisation, and early mover risks. The participants also critiqued the innovation fund and its suitability to support industrial decarbonisation that requires 10th, or even 200th of its kind projects instead of only innovative ones. The participants also problematised exposure to carbon price volatility, lack of support towards CCU, raised challenges with finding skilled workers, and argued that there is limited funding for storage projects.</p>
Uncertainty	9	<p>Uncertainty was a key challenge raised by the participants, fuelled by the other challenges and lack of information on the continuity of policy approaches, fragmented and complex funding schemes, and a lack of clear regulatory and policy framework for CCUS</p>

		implementation. The participants argued that this uncertainty can result in situation were actors wait, exacerbating the challenge.
Acceleration vs perfection	8	The participants argued that policies that aim for perfection can be detrimental to CCUS implementation and more broadly decarbonisation as this is in conflict with the aim of acceleration.
Coordination	12	The lack of coordination and clear, long-term and predictable regulatory and policy framework were among the key challenges raised by the participants, driven by the understanding that the challenge is complex and involves multiple actors with their own interests. This coordination was searched at different levels, from the EU to national and local levels. One of the participants raised that especially at the local and national level, this can be a question of capacity. Many challenges were connected to coordination, including that the decarbonisation targets for industry are too high, the storage development across the EU is uneven, the carbon accounting principles are unclear and fragmented, and the cost and length of permitting processes.
Politics	9	The politics related challenges connect to collaboration. Seven of the participants problematised the political and politicians' motivation and willingness to implement CCUS and raised concern over how for example election cycles can implement decision-making. Related to this, the participants discussed how Denmark could work as an example to kick of the political willingness for onshore CO ₂ storage.

3.2 Key enablers of CCUS deployment in Europe

Table 4 describes the key enablers raised by the participants.

Table 4: Key enablers of CCUS deployment

KEY ENABLERS OF CCUS DEPLOYMENT		
ENABLER CATEGORY	How many of the interviews raised this as a key enabler?	DESCRIPTION
Acceptance solutions	8	The acceptance of CCUS was often connected to the awareness of CCUS and climate change, and as such awareness raising was a commonly suggested solution. Other possible solutions included good community engagement and sharing benefits with local communities. Denmark's sustainable reputation was seen by the participants as a factor that can improve the acceptance of onshore storage as Denmark spearheads onshore CO ₂ storage development in Europe.
CO ₂ infrastructure solutions	11	Some of the most solutions to the infrastructure challenges included regulated assets-based models, the creation of CO ₂ standards, Denmark kicking-off CO ₂ storage in the EU, industrial clustering, and pipes dedicated to single emitters. The participants also argued for a clearer regulatory framework for CO ₂ storage and transport and increased information sharing on storage locations and characteristics. Four of the interviews also argued that UK should be included in the European CO ₂ transport and storage infrastructure.
Collaboration solutions	11	Solutions to improve collaboration between stakeholders raised by the participants include aggregation platform for CO ₂ transport and storage services, introduction of shared CO ₂ standards, and clear regulation for CO ₂ transport and storage and cross-border transport. The participants also raised information sharing between stakeholders as an important part of effective collaboration. Another key element of effective collaboration was responsibility sharing, and the Net Zero Industry Act and putting some of the responsibility on CO ₂ storage to oil and gas industries was seen as a positive measure. Last, the participants also raised trust building as a crucial solution to support effective collaboration.

Holistic solutions	7	The solutions raised in relation to the desire for a holistic approach connect directly to the solutions on coordination. In addition, the participants suggested that the revenues from polluting industries (from e.g. carbon tax, or EU ETS) should go back to decarbonising those industries. Two of the participants also argued that the climate case of CCU should be evaluated case-by-case.
Economics solutions	12	As with the economic challenges, the participants also raised many economic solutions. One of the most common economic solutions was a belief that instead of setting technologies and industries against each other, a free-market approach should be adopted (4 interviews). On the other hand, two of the interviews argued that steering of the market is necessary to support CCUS implementation. The many economic solutions raised by the participants include support targeted for CCUS, de-risking investment, Contracts-for-Difference model (Florence School of Regulation, 2023), responsibility sharing, streamlining of permitting processes, competitive funding, incentivisation, rewarding negative emissions, industrial clustering, carbon tax, demand side incentivisation, supporting carbon looping, shared ownership, green bonds, debt financing, and tax breaks.
Uncertainty solutions	4	The key solutions related to uncertainty include clear decisions on the policy approach, storage liability, and the role of CCUS in decarbonisation.
Acceleration vs perfection solutions	7	Some of the key solutions to the challenge of perfection versus acceleration raised by the participants include the streamlining of permitting processes, and a free-market policy approach.
Coordination solutions	11	Key solutions for coordination challenges included an overarching entity that would act as a facilitator for CCUS implementation, with two of the participants directly stating that the European Commission should be this entity. The key role of this facilitator

		<p>would be to kick-start CCUS development and market, positive discrimination of some Member States, enabling responsibility and information sharing and the streamlining of permitting processes.</p>
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3.3 Key enablers and barriers and Calcium Looping technology

Only a few of the participants had previous experiences with Calcium Looping technology and felt comfortable answering the question of whether Calcium Looping technology relates to any of the challenges and opportunities discussed during the interviews. These participants generally showed interest in Calcium Looping technology and saw it as one of the solutions in CCUS deployment. One participant was critical of Calcium Looping technology from a technical standpoint and saw the technology as too energy-intensive and saw the degradation of the sorbent as a limitation. It was also raised that Calcium Looping technology is not yet proven and is not being taken up by developers. Another participant argued that it could be a solution for the cement industry but was critical of it being a solution to for example the steel industry. As the CaLby2030 project aims to support the commercialisation of the technology and conducts research on how to improve the variables that impact the effectiveness of the technology, we can conclude that the CaLby2030 project is largely addressing the critique raised by the participants towards the technology and that the results of the project are of great interest to the interviewed stakeholder groups. The participants showed particular interest towards the business case analysis.

4 DISCUSSION

This section synthesises some of the barriers and enablers identified by the participants. Further analysis will be undertaken in upcoming studies related to Task 6.3. Here, the focus is on reporting the perspectives of the participants on the key enablers and barriers to CCUS implementation, without scrutinising how the results compare to existing knowledge about CCUS deployment.

The analysis of the interviews highlighted several recurring barriers to CCUS deployment in Europe. Many of these challenges are already well-known (CCUS Forum, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c), but the interviews highlighted the complexity and multi-faceted nature of these challenges. Among the key barriers identified by interview participants, issues such as the development of CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure, collaboration across stakeholders, economic challenges, and a lack of coordination and holistic approach were particularly prominent. These barriers are interconnected, with for example the economic case of CCUS relying on the development of CO₂ infrastructure. Both collaboration and the sharing of CO₂ infrastructure require a clear regulation and policy framework. The example that Denmark could provide in onshore storage development was seen as a key for both acceptance challenges as well as infrastructure challenges. Policy uncertainty is a central barrier to the economic case of CCUS, as the uncertainty can lead to an increased sense of risk and actors waiting for greater certainty instead of implementing CCUS projects. The results also showcase that the infrastructure challenge is also a justice challenge, as the uneven development of CO₂ storage can result in South and East Europe being left behind.

The participants proposed a wide range of solutions to overcome the barriers to CCUS implementation. Key suggestions included improving public acceptance through targeted awareness-raising campaigns and fostering good community engagement. Enhancing collaboration was another major focus, with participants advocating for the introduction of shared CO₂ standards and clear regulations, which would streamline infrastructure development and facilitate collaboration. Economic measures, such as de-risking investments through Contracts for Difference, streamlining permitting processes, and supporting market-based approaches, were also highlighted as essential to incentivising CCUS projects. Additionally, the participants emphasised the importance of coordinated efforts to ensure a unified approach across Europe. This coordination would help address regional disparities, such as uneven CO₂ storage development.

While this report provides an overview of the key barriers and enablers to CCUS deployment, it is important to note that the findings are based on participant perspectives and require further analysis. The complex interconnections between enablers and barriers, such as the relationship between infrastructure development, economic incentives, and policy frameworks, point to the need for more in-depth study, which will be undertaken in the future work of Task 6.3.

CONCLUSIONS

This report explained the key results of CCUS stakeholder interviews conducted for Task 6.3 of the CaLby2030 project. The semi-structured interviews were conducted with 12 CCUS stakeholders

representing diverse stakeholder groups and expertise areas. The analysis conducted for this report focused on identifying the key enablers and barriers raised by the participants of the interviews. This preliminary analysis will be followed up by a more in-depth and thematic analysis, including reflection on existing research insights, in future outputs of Task 6.3.

Many of the identified challenges are already well-known, but the interviews also resulted in less-known challenges and highlight the complexity and multi-dimensionality of the already known challenges. For example, it became clear from the interviews that the CO₂ transport and infrastructure challenge is not merely a challenge of scale, but also a deeply collaborative challenge with significant justice dimensions related to who will pay for and who will benefit from the infrastructure. Also, how can it be ensured that the infrastructure is sufficient throughout Europe? This sets justice as a both ethical but also as a regulatory challenge (see also Swennenhuis et al., 2022). The interviews will be further analysed with qualitative system dynamics modelling (Meadows, 2008b) and will be followed by Group Model Building (Vennix, 1996) sessions to investigate the causal relationships between the different enablers and barriers further. This sets the challenges and enablers in a systemic context and can help to identify intervention points (Meadows, 2008a) as well as further investigate the suitability of the enablers raised by the interview participants.

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Annex 1: Semi-structured interview protocol

- **Introduction of the researcher and the study, and an explanation of what happens during the interview.**
- **Chance for the participant to ask questions.**
- **Permission to start recording.**
- **Start of recording.**

Theme 1: Background and Expertise:

Example questions:

- First, can you tell me about your professional background and expertise related to CCUS?
- Next, can you tell me about the [company/organisation] and its interests/business related to CCUS?
- Is your expertise focused on a particular industry or geographical context?

Theme 2: Barriers to CCUS Implementation in Europe

Example questions:

- From your perspective, what are the main barriers to CCUS implementation in Europe?
- Are these challenges similar in Sweden/Spain/Germany/other countries?

Theme 3: CCUS in a national context

Example questions:

- What, in your view, are the key characteristics that shape CCUS deployment in the **country**?
- Are there any significant recent CCUS developments in the **country**?
- From an economic standpoint, do you believe that CCUS projects are currently viable in the **national** context, and what factors contribute to this?

Theme 4: Industry challenges and key characteristics

Example questions:

- What are the main challenges in implementing CCUS in the **steel industry/cement industry/ waste-to-power**?
- When thinking about all the different options for decarbonisation of **industry**, how does carbon capture compare to other options?

Theme 5: Impactful Policies or Regulations

Example questions:

- Are there specific regulatory gaps or areas that need attention and improvement to facilitate the deployment of CCUS technologies in **country**?

Theme 6: Challenges in International Collaboration

Example questions:

- Collaboration in carbon capture involves multiple actors across borders and the value chain. What, in your experience, are the main challenges for effective collaboration on CCUS?
- Considering the diverse interests and stakeholders involved, how can international collaboration in carbon capture be better supported?

Theme 7: EU-Level Support for CCUS

Example questions:

- What are your thoughts on the European Commission's Industrial Carbon Management Strategy? What is the good, the bad, and the could-be-better of the policy?
- What are your thoughts on the Net Zero Industry Act?
- What specific actions or policies do you think need to be implemented at the EU level to provide robust support for the development and deployment of CCUS technologies?

Theme 8: Social sustainability and justice

- What needs to be done to ensure that CCUS deployment is socially sustainable and fair?

Theme 9: Ideas for Problem Solutions

Example questions:

- How can the deployment of CCUS be better supported?
- Based on your expertise, do you have specific ideas or recommendations for addressing the challenges and issues we have discussed regarding CCUS implementation?
- What specific actions or policies do you think need to be implemented at the EU level to provide robust support for the development and deployment of CCUS technologies?

Theme 10: Calcium Looping Technology:

- Do you have experience with Calcium Looping Technology? How do you think calcium looping technology connects to the challenges and solutions we have discussed? Does it alleviate some of the challenges or make them worse?

Theme 11: Desired Outcomes for CCUS

Example questions:

- Looking forward, what outcomes or developments would you most like to see happen in relation to CCUS?
- If you had a magic wand, and could make anything happen in terms of CCUS implementation, what would that be?

Is there anything you would like to add?

End of the interview and explanation of how the results of the study will be shared with the participants.

Annex 2: Consent form

Informed consent for the ‘Societal readiness of CCUS technologies: a generic framework’ study

Introduction

You have been invited to participate in a scientific research project at Radboud University. Before you decide whether you want to participate in this study, you will receive an explanation of what the study entails. Please read this information carefully.

What is the study about?

This study is undertaken as a part of a European Union funded project CaLby2030 at Radboud University Nijmegen, Netherlands, and is funded under the Horizon Framework Programme (Grant Number: 101075416). This study focuses on investigating stakeholder perspectives on Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS), which is used to identify key enablers and barriers for CCUS deployment.

What is expected of you?

In this study, you will be interviewed by [researcher details] via Microsoft Teams. If you consent, an audio recording of the interview will be made to ensure the accuracy of the study. An interview will take approximately one hour. In the interview, we will ask you questions about what challenges and opportunities you see for CCUS based on your expertise in the field. These can relate to CCUS in general or CCUS in a specific country or industry. You will be asked questions about your specific CCUS experiences and expertise as well as general-level questions and opinions on CCUS policy and support. The interview will finish with questions about your thoughts on the future of CCUS. Examples of questions are:

1. What do you think are the main challenges for CCUS implementation in Sweden/Germany/Spain/Europe?
2. Based on your expertise, do you have specific ideas or recommendations for addressing the challenges and issues we have discussed regarding CCUS implementation?
3. Looking forward, what outcomes or developments would you most like to see happen concerning CCUS?
4. How do you perceive the potential contributions of CCUS to decarbonisation efforts?

Voluntary participation

You decide whether to participate in this study. Your participation is voluntary. You may say no at any time. You do not have to answer questions you would rather not answer, and you can stop your participation and withdraw your consent at any time during the study. You do not have to indicate why you are stopping. You can also have your research data and personal data deleted up to two weeks after participation, by sending an email to [researcher contact details].

What will happen to my data?

Your participation in this study is confidential. All research data will be stored on Radboud University's secure servers, according to the university's protocol. This protocol is in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The interviews will be written out. The recordings are deleted as soon as the interview report is finished. The interview report is pseudonymised, meaning that it is nearly impossible to trace data back to you. We do this by removing all information leading to you as an individual from the research data (such as your name, contact information, or any other mentioned individuals) and replacing it with a pseudonym.

The list of participants and pseudonyms is encrypted and stored in a secure environment to which only the researchers from the direct research team have access. Once this is done, the researchers will only work with pseudonymised data, which will also be used for scientific articles and presentations. The pseudonymised data may be used for other studies if you give your explicit consent. The pseudonymised interview reports will be stored on the Radboud network for ten years to ensure scientific integrity. The list of participants and pseudonyms will be deleted at the end of the study. The pseudonymised reports may be used for other studies by the researchers listed in this form. The reports, but only those that cannot be traced back to you, may also be shared and reused by other researchers if you provide your consent to this.

Ethical review and complaints

This study has been approved by the Ethics Assessment Committee Faculty of Law and Nijmegen School of Management [identification number of the ethical approval].

Should you nevertheless have complaints or problems you can always contact the main researcher: [researcher contact details].

You may also file a complaint with [details of formal complaint channels].

If you have questions or complaints about the processing of your personal data, we recommend that you first discuss them with the research team. You can also contact [contact details for more formal complaints].

Consent Statement

If you want to participate in this study, we will ask you to sign a consent form. Your written consent indicates that you have understood the information and agree to participate in the study. The consent form can be found on page 3 of this document.

Do you have any questions about the study?

If you would like to know more about the study or storage of the research data, please contact the main researcher.

Main researcher:

[contact details]

The research team:

[Contact details]

Consent form

I have been informed about the purpose of the study. I was able to ask questions about the study. I am participating in the study voluntarily. I understand that I may stop at any time during the study if I wish. I

understand how the data from the study will be kept and what it will be used for. I agree to participate in the study as described in the information document.

You can decide to consent only to some of the sections below.

I consent to (please check the appropriate box):

Yes No

- participating in the study.
- the making of [*audio*] recordings, which will be deleted after the data transcription and analysis.
- the reuse of the interview transcriptions, which cannot be traced back to the participant, for future research.

Signatures

Name of participant:

Date:

Signature:

Name of researcher:

Date:

Signature:

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